

Products from Hydrazines: Carbonyl Derivatives of Some α -Benzamido- β -2-benzofurylacrylohydrazides

D. S. Deorha and (Miss) Padma Gupta

In this communication are described a few characteristics of some hydrazones, obtained by condensing α -benzamido- β -(5-chloro-3,6-dimethyl-2-benzofuryl)-, -(5-chloro-3-ethyl-6-methyl-2-benzofuryl)-, and -(5-chloro-3-methyl-2-benzofuryl)-acrylohydrazides¹ with a few carbonyl compounds for a study of pharmacological screening. The preparation of the above acrylohydrazides has already been described¹.

Hydrazone.—To a solution of hydrazide (0.01M) in ethanol (20 ml) was added the carbonyl compound (0.01M) and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 15 min. On cooling, the solid hydrazone separating was crystallised from ethanol.

The colour of the needle-shaped hydrazones varied from light yellow to yellow. Characteristics, melting points, and analytical data of the acrylohydrazones prepared are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Carbonyl derivatives of the hydrazide.

Carbonyl compounds.	Melting points.			Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
	A.	B.	C.		Found.	Reqd.
Benzaldehyde	236°	201°	254-55°	A: C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	9.12	8.94
				B: C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.94	8.85
				C: C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	9.32	9.17
<i>m</i> -Nitro-benzaldehyde	275°	262°	275°	A: C ₂₇ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	11.08	10.74
				B: C ₂₈ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	10.74	10.35
				C: C ₂₆ H ₉ O ₅ N ₄ Cl	11.45	11.14
Piperonal	235°	242°	256-57°	A: C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.31	8.14
				B: C ₂₉ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.14	7.93
				C: C ₂₇ H ₂₀ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.53	8.37

1. Deorha and Gupta, this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 371.

TABLE I (contd.)

Carbonyl compound.	Melting points.			Formula	%Nitrogen.	
	A.	B.	C.		Found.	Reqd.
Cinnamaldehyde	204-65°	226°	228-29°	A: C ₂₀ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.66	8.44
				B: C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.53	8.20
				C: C ₂₈ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.71	8.57
Anisaldehyde	246-48°	223°	232°	A: C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.12	8.37
				B: C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.29	8.14
				C: C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.82	8.61
Vanillin	246°	253°	233°	A: C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.33	8.11
				B: C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.15	7.90
				C: C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.58	8.34
Furfural	245°	238°	252°	A: C ₁₅ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	9.23	9.10
				B: C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	9.03	8.83
				C: C ₂₄ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	9.57	9.38
<i>p</i> -Methylacetophenone	253-51°	215°	256°	A: C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.71	8.40
				B: C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.37	8.17
				C: C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.88	8.65
Salicylaldehyde	267°	253-54°	263°	A: C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.92	8.63
				B: C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.56	8.37
				C: C ₂₆ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	8.99	8.87
Acetophenone	261-62°	234°	228°	A: C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.81	8.65
				B: C ₂₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	8.56	8.40
				C: C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	9.01	8.90
Benzophenone	222°	252°	..	A: C ₃₃ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.92	7.66
				B: C ₃₄ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	7.36	7.48

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